

Original Research

Empowering Leadership Dimensions and Innovative Work Behaviors: The Moderating Role of Perceived Organizational Support

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been a heightened emphasis on fostering employee innovation and promoting innovative behaviors within the field of human resource management. In this context, the study investigated the impact of various dimensions of empowering leadership, including autonomy support and development support, on innovative work behaviors. Additionally, it explored the potential moderating role of perceived organizational support in this relationship. The research employed both descriptive and analytical methodologies with an applied focus. The statistical population comprised 723 employees from the Technical and Vocational Training Organization in Tehran, with a sample size of 322 participants. Data analysis was conducted using covariance-based structural equation modelling through the maximum likelihood method, utilizing SPSS and AMOS software. Findings indicated that empowering leadership significantly and positively influences innovative work behaviors, and this relationship is moderated by perceived organizational support.

Keywords: Autonomy support, development support, empowering leadership, innovative work behaviors.

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Introduction

There has been a significant surge in interest in enhancing employee innovation and innovative behavior in today's organizations as a competitive advantage (Sun et al., 2021). Based on research studies, it is widely accepted that innovation is crucial for the effectiveness of organizations (Khushk et al., 2023; Mariam, 2024; Sinaga et al., 2024). Innovation refers to the ability to create new products, services, technologies, and processes that provide a competitive advantage to organizations in both the private and public sectors (Al Kurdi et al., 2023; Dervitsiotis, 2010; Sarkar et al., 2022). Innovative Work Behaviors (IWBs), which involve developing, accepting, and implementing new ideas for products, technologies, and work methods, are considered to be an important asset for companies striving for innovation and success in today's dynamic environments (Ali et al., 2022; Sürücü et al., 2023). This is significant because innovation originates from individuals, and people's actions are crucial for continuous improvement in work processes, products, and services (Etikariena & Kalimashada, 2021).

Research has shown that the barriers to innovative work behaviors in the public sector are much broader than those in the private sector (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2013). In a world where continuous improvement and innovation are increasingly important and where organizations face reduced financial resources and increased demand for public services (Taylor-Gooby, 2012), these barriers can pose serious problems for the future performance and survival of public organizations.

The empowering leadership style, which encompasses the relationship between supervisors and employees, is a crucial aspect of the work environment. It significantly impacts employees' attitudes toward performance and their innovative efforts (Yuan & Woodman, 2010). Empowerment, as an organizational concept, can enhance employee productivity (Monje-Amor et al., 2021; Supriyanto et al., 2023). Given the business and technological changes in both the private and public sectors, organizations require empowered and productive employees (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2013). A highly skilled workforce, or knowledge workforce, is essential for today's organizations (Humphrey et al., 2007). In response to these changes, the concept of empowering leadership has emerged as a distinct form of leadership, focusing on empowering employees to increase work motivation by delegating more responsibilities and authority to lower organizational levels (Cheong et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2021).

There have been numerous studies focusing on the challenges and barriers faced by the public sector in fostering innovative work behaviors (Alipour & Karimi, 2018). However, there has been little explicit exploration of the role of empowering leadership in stimulating such behaviors. As most government agencies are under pressure to enhance service quality and safety, as well as increase efficiency, they need to develop and implement more efficient technologies and processes for their future performance and survival. However, there is limited research on empowering leadership and innovative work behaviors, which is the focus of this study. This research also emphasizes the importance of innovative activities for managers in government agencies and serves as a guide for enhancing innovative work behaviors among their employees.

The concept of innovative work behavior encompasses a broad range of actions. It includes individual actions that contribute to the creation, introduction, and application of beneficial innovations within an organization (Guo, Jin, et al., 2023; Hosseini & Haghghi Shirazi, 2021). These innovations may involve the development of new ideas or technologies, changes in administrative procedures to enhance working relationships, or the use of new ideas and technologies to improve work processes and organizational efficiency. In essence, any actions that lead to the production, processing, and application of new ideas to enhance the effectiveness and success of organizational processes are considered innovative behaviors (Alipour, Idris, & Karimi, 2011; Alipour, Idris, Ismail, et al., 2011; Purc & Lagun, 2019; Salam & Senin, 2022).

Several studies have focused on defining the structure of innovative work behaviors and outlining the specific steps involved in this process. For instance, Scott and Bruce (1994) distinguished between idea generation, idea promotion, and idea realization, while Kleysen and Streets (2001) identified the process of innovative work behavior as involving exploration, production, examination, formation, support, and application. Additionally, De Jong and Den Hartog (2010) emphasized idea exploration, idea generation, idea support, and implementation. In the current study, we will utilize the dimensions defined by Scott and Bruce (1994), specifically idea generation, idea promotion, and idea realization. The Innovative Work Behavior Process Model developed by Scott and Bruce (1994) is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Innovative Work Behavior Process Model
Source: Scott and Bruce (1994)

The innovation process often begins with identifying an opportunity or a problem (De Jong & Den Hartog, 2010). Opportunities may arise from failures, the gap between current and desired states, changes in industry and market structures, trends, or new processes developed in response to identified problems or failures (Drucker & Noel,

1986). Idea exploration and development involve seeking ways to enhance existing products or processes or solving problems by finding alternative solutions and reorganizing existing information and concepts (De Jong & Den Hartog, 2010). Once a new idea is generated, it needs to be promoted and supported, as it often faces resistance from existing business practices. To accomplish this, a strong coalition must be formed, resources mobilized, relevant stakeholders engaged, and potential risks considered, as the benefits of new ideas are often uncertain about the costs of development and implementation (Howell et al., 2005; Sheikhalishahi et al., 2020). Ultimately, implementing new ideas involves activities such as creating a sample or model of a product, technology, process, or new method of work and implementing it with a focus on achieving specific outcomes (Johnson et al., 2010). Additionally, if necessary, the prototype must be tested and modified, and the new way of working streamlined to innovate the organization's work processes (Khodabandeh-Yalabadi et al., 2024). Therefore, the final stage of the innovative work behavior process is tied to actual production, testing, and innovative implementation.

In recent times, there has been a growing interest in the concept of empowering leadership in the field of creativity and innovation. Empowering leadership refers to the intentional actions taken by leaders to share power with their employees, entrust them with more responsibilities, and allow them greater control over their work. Zhang & Bartol (2010), in a study, indicate that empowering leadership plays a crucial role in fostering employee innovation (Zhang & Bartol, 2010). They also discovered that the positive impact of leadership empowerment on creativity and innovation is mediated by individual factors such as the psychological empowerment of staff and creative self-efficacy. However, there is still a need for a deeper understanding of how empowering leadership influences underlying factors, which is crucial for promoting creativity. In our research, we have sought to explore the relationship between empowering leadership and the emergence of innovative work behaviors, as well as the moderating role of perceived organizational support.

Amundsen & Martinsen (2014) define empowering leadership as a way to motivate employees by sharing power and supporting their development. Empowering leadership is unique because it focuses on empowering followers and is related to participatory decision-making. It is also associated with transformational leadership and Leader-Member Exchange. Empowering leadership helps employees take on more responsibilities and develop their skills, which can lead to greater satisfaction and commitment (Johnson et al., 2010). Cheong et al. (2019) consider the various aspects of empowering leadership effectiveness. This includes exploring the potential non-linear main effects of empowering leadership on work-related outcomes, considering the possibility of reverse causation between empowering leadership and work-related outcomes, and examining the potential contradictory mediating mechanisms through which empowering leadership operates.

Creating conditions that psychologically empower employees is crucial for many organizations, and researchers have been studying this concept. According to Amundsen and Martinsen (2014), empowering leadership involves autonomy support and development support as its structural dimensions. Autonomy support means facilitating self-management, autonomy, power, and discretion in work, recognizing employees as

delegates with power and authority. Delegation of power and authority fosters self-determination and effectiveness in subordinates (Konczak et al., 2000). Encouraging employees to take personal initiative, make effective efforts, and learn self-management is essential for empowering leadership (Yun et al., 2006; Yukl, 2010). Additionally, empowering leaders should encourage employees to focus on goals, understand their capabilities and talents, and use their abilities to develop self-efficacy through emotional support and positive encouragement. In terms of development support, empowering leaders use visible models to systematically reflect effective self-leadership skills and other work-related behaviors for employees (Manz & Sims, 2001). Model learning is a component of the social cognitive theory, suggesting that behaviors can be learned or modified by observing others, especially those with power, success, or a specific position. Moreover, empowering leaders guide employees from dependence on leadership to self-esteem and independence through teaching, guidance, encouragement, and coaching. Empowerment fosters a sense of competence, performance, and skill, thereby increasing employee learning (Manz & Sims, 2001).

In a recent study, researchers found that empowering leadership, which involves promoting decision-making participation, expressing high-performance confidence, and providing autonomy, has a significant positive impact on employees' innovative behavior. Interestingly, emphasizing work significance does not have a significant effect on employees' innovation behavior. Additionally, job remodeling plays a significant role in promoting employee innovation behavior (Sun et al., 2021). In another study, researchers proposed a theoretical model to explore how empowering leadership influences employee innovative behavior (EIB). Drawing from self-determination theory and job characteristics theory, the study introduced meaningful work as a mediating variable and job complexity as a moderating variable. Data was collected from 6 private enterprises in China over three months (N = 272). The study employed hierarchical regression analysis, structural equation model analysis, and bootstrap analysis to test the proposed model. The results indicated that empowering leadership had a positive direct impact on EIB and also influenced EIB indirectly through meaningful work. Furthermore, job complexity was found to moderate the relationship between empowering leadership and EIB, as well as the relationship between meaningful work and EIB. This study offers a fresh perspective on how empowering leadership influences EIB (Guo, Peng, et al., 2023).

Additionally, the study revealed that job insecurity has a significant moderating effect on emphasizing work significance, promoting decision-making participation, expressing high-performance confidence, giving autonomy, and employees' innovative behavior. In a study, researchers found that leadership behaviors like personal development support and participative decision-making, as well as thriving at work, impact employee innovation behavior. They used Smart PLS to verify their model and found that personal development support and participative decision-making positively influence employee innovation behavior. Additionally, vigor and learning also have a positive influence on employee innovation behavior. Furthermore, personal development support moderates the relationship between participative decision-making and innovative behavior (Ye et al., 2022).

Eisenberger et al. introduced the concept of perceived organizational support in 1986, suggesting that it is influenced by various aspects of how the organization interacts with

its employees, including the frequency, severity, and assessment of rewards, recognition, compensation, job enrichment, and involvement in decision-making (Eisenberger et al., 2016). Organizational support, as perceived by individuals, reflects the belief that the organization values the cooperation, assistance, and well-being of its members (Eisenberger et al., 2016). The idea of perceived organizational support is based on social exchange theory (Casper et al., 2011), where employees who feel highly supported believe that the organization is responsive to their needs. This perception reflects the quality of social exchanges between the employee and the employer. Employees who perceive the organization as supportive tend to develop an emotional connection with the organization, as they believe that the organization values their efforts and cares about their well-being (Casimir et al., 2014; Eisenberger et al., 2016). Research has shown that high perceived organizational support is associated with positive outcomes such as increased emotional commitment, improved performance, and reduced turnover intention (Dai & Qin, 2016; Eisenberger et al., 2016; Luo, 2020). Additionally, leaders' support for employees positively impacts employees' attitudes and behaviors, reducing employees' turnover intention and increasing their happiness (Romão et al., 2022). A meta-analysis study by Kurtessis et al. (2017) examined the relationship between perceived organizational support and leadership styles. It found that transformational leadership, as well as leader-member exchange and exchange leadership, are positively related to perceived organizational support. These leadership styles contribute to employees feeling valued and supported by the organization. Therefore, it seems that perceived organizational support may act as a moderator between leadership styles and innovative work behaviors.

Generally speaking, Empowering leadership is a vital dimension in organizational settings, fostering an environment where employees feel encouraged and supported to engage in innovative work behaviors. This study aims to address the research problem of understanding how specific empowering leadership dimensions, namely autonomy support and development support, influence employees' innovative work behaviors. The significance of this topic lies in its potential to enhance organizational performance and competitive advantage through the cultivation of innovation at the individual employee level.

Despite the growing interest in empowering leadership and its effects on innovation, a research gap persists in comprehending the moderating role of perceived organizational support in this relationship. Previous studies have highlighted the importance of leadership in promoting innovation, yet there is limited empirical evidence on how perceived organizational support may enhance or weaken the impact of empowering leadership on innovative work behaviors.

The background of existing studies underscores the critical role of leadership in fostering innovation. Research by Bandura (1977) and subsequent scholars has demonstrated that leaders who provide autonomy support enable employees to exercise creativity and take initiative in their work. Similarly, development support from leaders has been shown to motivate employees to acquire new skills and apply them innovatively (Burhan & Khan, 2024). However, the interaction

between these empowering leadership dimensions and perceived organizational support remains underexplored. In addressing this gap, the current study investigates the following hypotheses:

H1: Autonomy support has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviors.

H2: Development support has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviors.

H3: Perceived organizational support moderates the relationship between autonomy support and innovative work behaviors.

H4: Perceived organizational support moderates the relationship between development support and innovative work behaviors.

By exploring these hypotheses, this research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how empowering leadership and organizational support jointly influence innovative work behaviors, thereby contributing valuable insights to both academic literature and practical applications in organizational development.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of research

Methodology

The research is practical and utilizes a descriptive-analytic correlation method to analyze the relationship between variables, specifically using structural equations. The study's statistical population consists of 723 employees of the Tehran Technical and Vocational Training Organization. It is crucial to determine the minimum sample size for structural equation modeling. While there is no general rule for the minimum or recommended number of observations for CFA, Tinsley & Brown (2000) suggest that at

least 200 observations are advisable for anything beyond the simplest CFA model. To obtain a more representative sample of the population, the researchers sent the questionnaire to 400 employees using the online questionnaire method. After collecting the data, the researchers received 322 completed questionnaires, which were analyzed as the sample size.

Standard questionnaires were used to collect data. The Empowering Leadership Questionnaire by Amundsen and Martinson (2014), comprising two dimensions and 18 items, was used to measure the dimensions of the empowering leadership variable. The Janssen (2000) Questionnaire with three dimensions and nine items was used to measure innovative work behaviors. To assess perceived organizational support, a questionnaire developed by Eisenberger et al. (1986) containing 16 items was used. Following the selection of the questionnaires, steps were taken to assess their validity and reliability. The content validity method was used to validate the tools, and the questionnaire was approved by academic experts. Additionally, the reliability of the questionnaires was assessed by evaluating the internal consistency of the items using Cronbach's alpha. The reliability coefficient for the research variables is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Cronbach's alpha coefficients

Variables	Items	Alpha coefficients
Development Support	6	0.815
Autonomy Support	12	0.847
Innovative work behaviors	9	0.920
Perceived organizational support	16	0.788

In order to analyze the data, various statistical analysis methods were utilized. These include Pearson correlation analysis to calculate correlation coefficients, structural equation modeling to confirm the fit of the structural equation model with the collected data, and moderation analysis as outlined by Cohen et al. (2013) to investigate the role of a moderator variable.

Findings

Descriptive findings

Table 2 presents the descriptive results of the data, including frequency distribution and percentage of subjects by gender, age, marriage, education, and KMO coefficient (sampling adequacy index).

Table 2. Demographic Findings

No	Variable	Indicator	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	71
		Female	29
2	Age	Less than 30	17
		31-40	30
		41-50	33

No	Variable	Indicator	Percentage
		More than 50	20
3	Marriage	Married	81
		Single	19
4	Education	Diploma	14
		Bachelor	41
		MA	27
		PhD	18
5	KMO	0.781	

Correlation test between variables

In structural equation modeling, the use of latent variables relies on the presence of a correlation between the variables. To examine this, we performed a Pearson correlation analysis, which reveals the direction and strength of the linear relationship between two variables. The correlation coefficients can be found in Table 3. The coefficients in the table show a positive and satisfactory correlation. The average correlation coefficient for all variables is above average.

Table 3. Correlation between variables

Variables	Autonomy Support	Development Support	POS	IWB
Autonomy support	1			
Development support	0.84**	1		
POS	0.61**	0.57**	1	
IWB	0.61**	0.60**	0.75**	1

** $P \geq 0/01$

Also, the mean, standard deviation (SD), and Cronbach's alpha of variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Average, standard deviation, alpha coefficients of variables

Variables	Mean	SD	Alpha
Autonomy Support	3.30	0.64	0.94
Development Support	3.43	0.65	0.87
POS	3.34	0.50	0.91
IWB	3.19	0.61	0.89
Idea Generation	3.20	0.63	0.68
Idea Promotion	3.23	0.72	0.89
Idea Realization	3.16	0.71	0.82

Structural Equation Modeling and Model Fit

Before fitting the structural equation model, the measurement models are evaluated by conducting a confirmatory factor analysis using the Amos software. The evaluations utilized software output fitting indexes to assess the significance of factor loads for

different constructs of the questionnaire. The values for the general factor analysis model can be found in Table 6. Initially, each measurement model was examined individually, followed by an examination of the overall measurement model. In both stages of factor analysis, the regression weights for all items and dimensions were significant at a 95% confidence level. The significance level for the items was less than 0.05, indicating their meaningfulness. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis for meaningful items, as well as the fitting indices of the confirmatory factor analysis model, are presented in Table 5. These indices demonstrate the fit of the measurement models, with all the factor loads of the items and dimensions being significant.

Table 5. Fitness indices

Variable	CFI	CMIN/DF	P	RMSEA
Autonomy Support	0.953	2.43	0.00	0.095
Development Support	1.00	0.651	0.735	0.001
POS	0.878	1.247	0.650	0.039
IWB	0.936	2.38	0.528	0.093

The results of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the partial index P were examined to determine the probability of the factor load being considered for each variable. It was found that the factor loads and the P value were both less than 0.05, indicating that the questions effectively measured the observed variables. The structural equation model allows researchers to analyze both observed and latent variables simultaneously (Tinsley & Brown, 2000). When using the structural equation model, it is important to evaluate how well the hypothesized model fits with the observed data. Researchers often use the Goodness of Fit Index to assess this fit. RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error Approximation) is an important index (Tinsley & Brown, 2000). It is commonly used in confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation models. According to McCallum and Austin (2000), if the RMSEA value is less than 0.01, the model's fitness is excellent. If it is between 0.01 and 0.05, the fitness of the model is good, and if it is between 0.05 and 0.08, it is considered average. Please take note of the following text:

According to studies, an RMSEA value below 0.08 is considered acceptable (MacCallum & Austin, 2000). Another index used to assess fit is the Chi-square probability index (X^2), which indicates how well the theoretical model aligns with the actual data. This statistic tends to increase with larger sample sizes and more observed variables. In a good structural equation model, the Chi-square ratio should have a degree of freedom less than 3, and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) should be greater than 0.9 (Tinsley & Brown, 2000). For the fitted structural equation model, the Chi-square value is 441.84, the Chi-square ratio to degrees of freedom is 2.63, and the root mean squared error approximation is 0.084. All the fit indices of the final model are desirable, indicating a satisfactory fit of the model. The results of the general fit indices of the conceptual model are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Structural model fit indices

CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF	RMSEA
441.84	168	0.00	2.63	0.084

The software output includes the factor loads and regression coefficients, which are as follows:

Figure 3. Structural Model

In this study, two critical indices, CR and P, and regression coefficients were used to test the significance of the hypotheses. Based on the significance level of 0.05, the critical value should be greater than 1.96. If the parameter value is less than this, it is not important in the template (Tinsley & Brown, 2000). Also, a significance level less than 0.05 for P indicates a significant difference in the calculated value for regression weights with a zero value at the 0.95 level (Tinsley & Brown, 2000). The results of the structural equation model showed that the two main hypotheses of this research, the significance of the impact of autonomy support and development support on innovative work behaviors, are confirmed at a 95% confidence level. The results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Test results of the first and second hypotheses

Hypothesis	Regression Coefficient	CR	P	Result
1- Autonomy support a positive and significant effect on innovative behaviors	0.80	3,97	0,00	accepted
2- Development support has a positive and significant effect on innovative behaviors	0,60	0,60	0,00	accepted

To test the moderating hypothesis, we used multiple hierarchical regression analysis in the SPSS software. The moderating effect is the significance of the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Following the method proposed by Cohen et al. (2003), we utilized multiple hierarchical regressions to analyze the role of perceived organizational support. The study employs hierarchical regression analysis to examine the moderation effect, a method recognized for its robustness in analyzing moderator variables. This approach enables a clear distinction between independent variables (autonomy support and development support) and the moderator (perceived organizational support) by assessing changes in explained variance (R^2) and the significance of interaction terms. It ensures statistical rigor by systematically testing moderation effects through changes in R^2 and F-statistics while mitigating multicollinearity by creating standardized interaction variables. The statistically significant β values at a 95% confidence level validate the moderating role of perceived organizational support, providing comprehensive insights into its influence on the relationships between variables and aligning effectively with the research objectives (Aguinis, 1995).

To analyze the moderator variable, independent and moderator variables needed to be standardized to reduce the correlation between them. This helps to decrease the probability of multicollinearity. The interaction variable was created by multiplying the standardized independent and moderator variables. In the first stage, the predictor and modifier variables were used, and in the second stage, the interaction variable entered the regression model. The analytical results of the effect of the moderator variable (perceived organizational support) on the relationship between two independent variables (autonomy support and development support) on the dependent variable (innovative business behaviors) are shown in Tables 8 and 9. The moderating role of perceived organizational support was confirmed.

Table 8. Moderate test results of perceived organizational support

Hierarchical regression	Independent variable	dependent variable	β	R2	Change Statistics	
					R2 change	F Change
First stage	Autonomy Support	IWB	$\frac{0.238}{0.604}$	0.592	0.592	84.752
	POS		0.254			
Second stage	Autonomy Support	IWB	0.610	0.593	0.001	0.156
	POS					
	Interaction Variable		0.032			

The significance of R^2 was initially determined using hierarchical regression analysis to confirm the presence of a moderator variable. The significance of the f changes also indicated the presence of a moderator variable (Hair Jr. et al., 2019). The significance of the β value for the interaction variable was then examined. The value was found to be 0.032, which is statistically significant at a confidence level of 0.95, confirming the third hypothesis. This supports the idea that perceived organizational support moderates the

relationship between autonomy support and innovative work behaviors. Additionally, the β value in Table 9 was found to be 0.038, which is statistically significant at a confidence level of 0.95, confirming the fourth hypothesis. This suggests that perceived organizational support moderates the relationship between development support and innovative work behaviors.

Table 9. Moderate test results of perceived organizational support

Hierarchical regression	Independent variable	dependent variable	β	R2	Change Statistics	
					R2 change	F Change
First stage	Development Support	IWB	0.268	0.605	0.605	89.491
	POS		0.593			
Second stage	Development Support	IWB	0.284	0.606	0.001	0.234
	POS		0.606			
	Interaction Variable		0.038			

Conclusion and Recommendations

Today, organizations no longer rely solely on professionals, scientists, and R&D specialists but also harness the innovative capabilities of their employees. Innovative work behaviors are crucial for introducing new ideas, processes, products, or methods within a role, group, or organization. This innovative employee behavior enhances an organization's ability to innovate, providing a sustainable competitive advantage. This study aimed to explore the impact of leadership behaviors on fostering innovative work behaviors, utilizing the empowering leadership style due to its nature in empowering employees.

Numerous researchers and managers have sought to identify factors influencing innovative work behaviors. Since innovation is not an individual activity, individuals' innovative behavior is influenced by interactions with others. Employees within an organization rely on their leaders for information, resources, and support in producing, developing, and implementing new ideas. As such, the role of a leader is a significant driving force behind individuals' innovations. The key question is how leaders can enhance their employees' innovative work behaviors. In this study, we sought a concept that effectively stimulates innovation within the workplace. Empowering leadership encompasses behaviors that encourage people to generate new ideas, processes, products, or practices within their roles, groups, or organizations. Empowering leadership comprises two key concepts: development support and autonomy support. Autonomy support includes delegation, coordination, information sharing, encouragement of initiative, goal alignment, self-efficacy and motivation, and inspirational support. Development support entails modeling behaviors as well as providing guidance and direction toward self-leadership.

The impact of empowering leadership on innovative work behaviors can be better understood by considering a moderating variable. This concept has been explored through the lens of perceived organizational support in various research studies. While empowering leadership aims to encourage employee innovation, it's crucial to consider how employees interpret this support in fostering innovative behaviors. Even if a supervisor encourages an individual to generate and implement new ideas, the results indicate that employee perception plays a significant role in enhancing organizational support for promoting innovative work practices.

To test the research hypotheses regarding the influence of empowering leadership dimensions on innovative work behaviors and the moderating effect of perceived organizational support, a research questionnaire was distributed to employees of the Tehran Technical and Vocational Training Organization in Iran, which constituted the statistical population.

The research findings demonstrated that the dimensions of empowering leadership, specifically autonomy support and development support, have a positive and significant impact on innovative work behaviors within the workplace. When organizational members perceive that their leaders are supportive of innovative initiatives, they are more motivated. Empowering leadership, which entails trusting employees and granting them autonomy and authority, leads to the generation of creative ideas and facilitates their development and implementation. These findings underscore the crucial role of leaders and managers in motivating employees to exhibit innovative work behaviors.

The study's findings in the public sector organization are consistent with a study by Scott and Bruce (1994), which highlighted the importance of effective communication between leaders and employees in encouraging innovative behaviors. In a public sector setting, an environment that supports innovation and values creative ideas without fear of backlash, promotes innovative work behaviors. This aligns with a study by Bain et al. (2001), which emphasized the significance of fostering creativity and innovation, as well as providing necessary resources for implementing creative ideas, in driving innovation among government employees. Additionally, perceived organizational support plays a key role in cultivating innovative work behaviors. When employees feel supported by their leaders, they are more likely to generate and present creative ideas and strive to be innovative to advance within the organization. Empowering leaders can instill a culture of innovation through behaviors such as empowerment, encouragement of initiative, and fostering employee self-efficacy.

In recent years, the interplay between leadership styles and employee behavior has garnered significant attention in organizational psychology. One salient aspect of this relationship is the concept of empowering leadership, which is characterized by leaders who promote autonomy, encourage participation in decision-making, and foster a supportive environment. The theoretical and practical implications of the findings related to empowering leadership dimensions and innovative work behaviors, particularly concerning the moderating role of perceived organizational support, are profound.

Theoretically, the research suggests that empowering leadership dimensions significantly influence innovative work behaviors among employees. Empowering

leaders create an environment where employees feel valued and motivated to contribute their ideas and creative solutions. This aligns with the social exchange theory, which posits that positive leader behaviors lead to reciprocal positive outcomes from employees. Furthermore, the moderation of perceived organizational support indicates that employees who perceive their organization as supportive are more likely to engage in innovative behaviors when led by empowering leaders. This finding enhances our understanding of the conditions under which leadership styles can effectively promote innovation. It also suggests that researchers should consider the contextual factors, such as organizational culture and employee perceptions, when studying the impact of leadership on innovation.

From a practical standpoint, organizations can leverage the insights from this research to enhance their leadership development programs. By training leaders in empowering behaviors, organizations can cultivate a culture that encourages innovation. Additionally, organizations should focus on fostering a supportive environment, as perceived organizational support amplifies the positive effects of empowering leadership on innovative work behaviors. This can involve initiatives such as recognizing employee contributions, providing resources for creativity, and ensuring open communication channels. Ultimately, by integrating empowering leadership practices with a strong focus on organizational support, companies can create a dynamic workplace that not only encourages innovation but also retains talented employees eager to contribute to the organization's success.

The findings suggest that government leaders and managers should be mindful that overly formal structures and rigid laws and regulations can hinder the development of innovative work behaviors. Complex organizational structures, excessive bureaucracy, and rigid rules impede quick responses to the changing needs of both internal and external stakeholders of government organizations. Previous researchers found that high levels of organizational formality and complexity, characterized by rigid methods, strict regulations, tight budget controls, and a lack of flexibility in innovative processes, significantly limit innovative work behaviors in government organizations (Boyne & Walker, 2004). Therefore, it is recommended that managers of government organizations foster a culture of cooperation and support to encourage innovation among their employees. They should guide their employees toward the organization's goals and assure them that their creative ideas will be supported. Employees should be encouraged to take initiative and even be rewarded proportionally. This study suggests that organizations should encourage leaders to merge more coaching skills into their leadership styles. By empowering them, managers can increase their self-efficacy and make them feel more empowered. By reducing formal rules and intense controls, managers can support employees in proposing and implementing creative ideas that align with the organization's goals.

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